

Exploring RRI in Bioprinted Organoids: Reflections from the ENLIGHT project

European
Innovation
Council

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964497.

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1. AUTHORS

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti (FGB) was established in Milan in 1994. In 2024, it was officially recognized as a Third Sector Entity (ETS). The purpose of the Foundation is to promote, in line with the values expressed by the Bassetti family, the responsible practice of innovation at both the national and international levels.

Since 2004, when it played a pioneering role in the organization of one of the first consensus conferences in Italy, FGB has strengthened its expertise in the design and implementation of participatory processes related to technoscience. These range from public deliberation models for policymaking (such as mini-publics and citizen juries) to structured multi-stakeholder co-creation pathways, operating at various levels (local, regional, national, and European).

Since the second decade of the 2000s, FGB has contributed to building, experimenting with, and consolidating the principles and practices of RRI through the design, coordination, and implementation of numerous projects funded by the European Commission and other public and private entities. Among these are SMART-map (EU H2020), TRANSFORM (EU H2020), MOSAIC (EU H2020), ENLIGHT (EU H2020), FETA, CO-VALUE (EU Horizon Europe) and GINEVRA (Interreg Central Europe), all aimed at supporting regions, institutions, and public and private organizations in developing approaches capable of aligning research and innovation decisions and processes with societal needs, expectations, and values.

Since 2023, FGB has been coordinating the [REINFORCING](#) project (EU Horizon Europe), aimed at establishing the central virtual European hub for Open and Responsible Research and Innovation to collect and gather ORRI experiences and tools to support R&I actors across the ERA.

2. INTRODUCTION

Within the [ENLIGHT](#) project, Fondazione Giannino Bassetti (FGB) was responsible for leading Task 6.3 on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).

FGB provided training on the RRI approach throughout the project, highlighting its key principles and dimensions through dedicated modules delivered during ENLIGHT project meetings (online and in person).

In addition, FGB conducted a desk-based analysis of the socio-ethical implications of the technologies central to the project, with a particular focus on organoid research and its potential future clinical applications. Key findings from this analysis were discussed during a workshop held with ENLIGHT partners, with a dual objective: to reflect on the ethical and societal impact of the research conducted under ENLIGHT, and to set the stage for defining a set of recommendations for the broader European organoid research community.

This report summarizes the RRI pathway within the [ENLIGHT](#) project.

▼ Example of a bioprinter from ENLIGHT partner Readily3D.
Photocredit: Readily3D

3. ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIO-ETHICAL IMPACT OF R&I ACTIVITIES PERFORMED BY THE ENLIGHT PROJECT

This analysis, guided by the Responsible Research and Innovation approach, encompasses the societal and ethical aspects of organoids research, a core feature of the ENLIGHT project.

Leveraging a synergy of expertise across diverse technological and biotechnological sectors, including 3D bioprinting, photonics, and synthetic biology, the project explored an innovative approach to bioprint an artificial human pancreas using patient-derived stem cells. ENLIGHT aimed to advance health therapies, particularly by providing a promising tool for testing new treatments for diabetes.

Even if some specific societal concerns and ethical issues of organoids which are produced thanks to bioprinting have been considered, the socio-ethical analysis illustrated in this report deliberately excluded examining the socio-ethical dimensions associated with each of the individual technologies implemented under the ENLIGHT project, namely genome editing, synthetic biology, 3D bioprinting, and optogenetics. Although each of these technologies carries its own set of ethical challenges and societal considerations, such issues fall outside the scope of this study.

Furthermore, the analysis did not address the societal and ethical considerations intertwined with organoid research in the context of brain science, since this area was not within the focus of the ENLIGHT project. This specific area of research introduces highly distinctive and complex ethical concerns, including debates around consciousness, identity, and the moral status of brain organoids. These considerations, while critically important, involve nuanced societal implications that require separate, focused discussion beyond the remit of the current analysis.

Lastly, this analysis is far from exhaustive. Further initiatives, including EU-funded projects, have devoted more time and effort than ENLIGHT could dedicate to a thorough assessment of the ethical and societal aspects of organoid research. Many elements derived from these studies have been considered and incorporated into this report, whose primary aim was to initiate an RRI journey with ENLIGHT researchers, technologists and innovators, with the hope of continuing the dialogue well beyond the duration of the project.

3.1 Responsible Research and Innovation

In recent decades, the scientific community has witnessed a growing imperative to reshape the relationship between science and society. Nowhere is this more critical than in the health field, where the societal impact of research and innovation (R&I) directly influences public well-being, trust in science, and the ethical legitimacy of new technologies.

The concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) has emerged as a comprehensive framework designed to ensure that R&I processes are inclusive, ethically grounded, anticipatory, and socially responsive. RRI represents a paradigm shift in science governance, moving away from traditional, one-directional models of knowledge production toward a model grounded in co-creation and public engagement and beyond traditional scientific standards like research integrity, ethical review, or codes of conduct, encompassing a forward-

looking and anticipatory governance of potential unintended and undesirable consequences (Owen et al., 2012).

It addresses the growing complexity of scientific progress and its socio-ethical implications, especially salient in fields of controversial scientific artifacts and emerging technologies applied to the health sector (Simone et al., 2025).

3.1.1 Origins and Evolution of RRI

The institutionalisation of RRI within the European research landscape can be traced to the early 2000s, when public trust in science was increasingly strained due to controversies such as the BSE crisis and genetically modified organisms for the food sector, and food safety scares. These events highlighted the limitations of conventional scientific governance, which often overlooked societal concerns and treated public unease as stemming from ignorance or misinformation (Owen et al., 2021).

In response, the European Commission (EC) began advocating for a more open, inclusive, and reflexive approach to science and innovation. The seminal moment came with the publication of the EC White Paper on Governance (2001), which called for more democratic and participatory governance models. This laid the groundwork for the RRI concept, which gained formal recognition with its articulation by von Schomberg in 2011, in which RRI is defined as *“a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability, and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products.”*

This framing marked a departure from the risk-based and ex-post ethical assessment paradigms that had dominated prior R&I governance models.

RRI has been a recursive element of the EU Framework Programmes for Research (and then for Research and Innovation) and reached its institutional peak during the EU’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, as a way to guide research and innovation to address major societal challenges, including those related to health, food security, clean energy, transport, and climate change (European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2014)). RRI was referenced explicitly in EU Regulation 1291/2013, integrated as a cross-cutting theme under Science with and for Society (SwafS), and operationalised through dozens of funded projects that embedded RRI principles into research governance, including in health-related domains (Simone, 2018).

The transition to Horizon Europe has broadened the scope further (Robinson et al., 2020), embedding RRI into the overarching agenda of Open Science, giving rise to the concept of Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) (Simone et al., 2025).

Globally, RRI has inspired parallel developments, such as Responsible Innovation (RI) in the U.S., where it has been linked to programs under the National Nanotechnology Initiative (Guston, 2012), and similar approaches in China (Wang et al., 2023).

3.1.2 Dimensions and Principles of RRI

At the heart of RRI lies a set of normative dimensions and principles that shape both its philosophical underpinnings and practical implementation. These include, as defined by Stilgoe et al. (2013):

- **Anticipation:** anticipation involves proactive assessment of potential risks, benefits, and societal implications of emerging health technologies at an early stage, before trajectories

become locked in.

- **Reflexivity:** Encouraging researchers and institutions to critically examine their own assumptions, values, and responsibilities, especially relevant in ethically charged domains like gene editing or AI diagnostics
- **Inclusiveness and Responsiveness:** RRI calls for iterative, inclusive processes in which innovation pathways can be redirected in response to a broad variety of stakeholder input and evolving societal needs.

From an operational point of view, RRI encompasses open science practices and transparent communication of research goals, processes, and outcomes of R&I but also structured involvement of citizens, patients, stakeholders, and civil society organisations in shaping together R&I trajectories.

3.1.3 RRI in emerging biomedical research, technologies and innovation

The rapid evolution of biomedical technologies—particularly in the realm of organoids and bioprinting—promises transformative breakthroughs in medicine, offering novel solutions for drug testing, regenerative therapies, and personalized treatments. These innovations mark a profound shift in how we model disease, explore therapeutic interventions, and envision the future of healthcare. However, the future of health research lies not only in technological capability but also in the ability of science to listen, adapt, and align with societal values and ethical sensitivities around, for instance, data privacy, informed consent, and potential research misuse.

In this context, the framework of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) serves as a needed ethical and democratic infrastructure. RRI ensures that research is not only scientifically sound but also responsibly conducted, socially inclusive, and publicly accountable. This becomes especially important in areas like organoids research and bioprinted research (Vermeulen et al., 2017), where the implications of manipulating living cells into functional tissue structures go far beyond the lab bench and into deeply contested societal, ethical, and philosophical domains.

A critical challenge that RRI helps to confront is the Collingridge dilemma, a central paradox in the governance of emerging technologies. First articulated by David Collingridge in 1980, this dilemma highlights a tension: in the early stages of technological development, it is easiest to steer innovation, but hardest to predict its impacts; conversely, once a technology is widely adopted and its effects become clear, it becomes extremely difficult to change course.

This dilemma is definitely relevant in organoid research and innovation. At the early experimental stage, such as in projects like ENLIGHT, society still has a window of opportunity to influence the direction of research. Yet, this is precisely the stage when uncertainty about long-term risks and implications is greatest. Without proactive ethical foresight and participatory governance, this uncertainty can lead to irreversible trajectories with unintended consequences, technological lock-ins, ethical oversights, or social inequities.

RRI addresses the Collingridge dilemma by embedding principles of anticipation, reflexivity, inclusiveness, and responsiveness directly into the research process. In doing so, it enables researchers and stakeholders to envision multiple futures, explore societal impacts early on, and maintain the flexibility to be responsive as knowledge evolves.

Moreover, RRI challenges the traditional, top-down approach to health research by supporting

co-creation and participatory decision-making. It empowers marginalized voices, including patients with rare diseases, underrepresented populations, and resource-limited communities, to actively shape research priorities and ensure that innovation addresses real-world needs.

RRI can also contribute to trust-building by fostering transparency, enabling open access to research data and results, and involving the public in shaping the directions of research. Through these practices, health innovation gains greater legitimacy and social acceptance.

3.2 Organoids: From Research to Clinical Settings – An Introduction

Organoids are three-dimensional cell structures in vitro that mimic the functions of real human organs. More recently, as also pursued in the ENLIGHT project, organoids have been combined with additive manufacturing techniques to enable architectural control over cell assembly in 3D, to better capture the composition and function of human tissues. These advanced organoid technologies have rapidly emerged as pivotal tools in biomedical research and regenerative medicine.

Derived primarily from pluripotent stem cells or adult stem cells, organoids simulate complex tissue environments, offering researchers a powerful platform for studying human biology, modeling diseases, testing drugs, and potentially repairing damaged tissues and organ transplantation (Huang et al., 2025).

Over the past decade, organoid technology has evolved. The differentiation protocols have become more standardized, enabling reproducible generation of organoids with cell-type diversity and architectural fidelity. Furthermore, although many challenges remain to be addressed, 3D bioprinting technologies have become increasingly significant in tissue engineering and organoid development due to their ability to replicate intricate architectures, potentially mimicking both the cellular organization and structural characteristics of biological tissues and organs and thereby shaping the cellular microenvironment and influencing cell behavior (Zandrini et al., 2022).

For the innovation ecosystem—comprising university researchers, biotech startups, healthcare institutions, and regulatory bodies—organoids are poised to revolutionize clinical research and patient care.

As organoids move from the bench to bedside, they bring with them profound opportunities—and responsibilities.

3.2.1 Applications in Biomedical Research

Organoids have rapidly gained traction in basic research. One of the most relevant uses of organoids is in disease modeling. Organoids derived from patient-specific cells allow researchers to recreate and study disease processes in a controlled laboratory environment.

This is particularly valuable for investigating the pathophysiology of genetic, infectious, and degenerative diseases. Moreover, the introduction of CRISPR/Cas9 genome-editing tools into organoid systems enables researchers to mimic disease-causing mutations and study their consequences, offering a dynamic platform for functional genomics.

These insights not only advance fundamental biology but also inform strategies for tissue engineering and organ fabrication, paving the way for artificial organogenesis using patient-derived cells.

In infectious disease research, organoids have proven instrumental in studying host-pathogen interactions and the complex biology during viral infections, such for example in liver (Caiazza et al., 2021), revealing tissue-specific immune responses that were not observable in traditional 2D cultures or animal models.

Organoids offer also significant advantages in preclinical drug development and toxicological screening. Because they more accurately mimic human tissue physiology, organoids potentially reduce the reliance on animal testing and bridge the translational gap between laboratory and clinical outcomes. Furthermore, organoids can be used to evaluate off-target effects, drug metabolism, and organ-specific toxicity.

Tumor-derived organoids can be cultured from cancer patients' biopsies to test chemotherapeutic agents and targeted therapies in a personalized manner. This approach enables clinicians to predict drug responsiveness and tailor treatment plans, thus enhancing the effectiveness of precision oncology (Drost and Clevers, 2018), or can provide new tools to monitor cancer early progression and target drug efficacy, especially for wide-spread tumors like pancreatic adenocarcinoma (Sgarminato et al., 2024). Additionally, co-culture systems combining organoids with immune cells are being developed to study tumor-immune interactions, immune evasion, and response to immunotherapy, which are critical in designing next-generation cancer treatments (Veninga and Voest, 2021).

Organoids are also valuable in studying rare genetic disorders that are difficult to model in animals. Since organoids can be derived from patient-specific induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs), they provide an unparalleled opportunity to investigate the biology of orphan diseases at a cellular level. Furthermore, these models can support not only scientific discovery but also the development of orphan drugs and gene therapies.

3.2.2 Clinical and Translational Horizons

The translational potential of organoids lies in regenerative and precision medicine.

Researchers are exploring ways to use pancreatic, liver, intestinal, and retinal organoids to repair or replace damaged tissues and restore organ function. Organoids derived from a patient's own cells also open the door to autologous transplantation, reducing the risk of immune rejection.

Early clinical translation of organoid technologies is underway, particularly in the context of implants, patches, and bioengineered constructs, like in the case of the pancreatic islet-like organoids for insulin secretion in experimental diabetes therapies. Most of these are still at the preclinical or Phase I trial stages and are regulated under compassionate use or experimental designations.

The field is evolving quickly, driven by innovation consortia, public-private partnerships, and increased venture capital investment in clinical-stage organoid companies.

3.3 Socio-ethical considerations on organoids

While ethical discussions around brain organoids have attracted significant attention due to concerns about consciousness and sentience, non-neural organoids pose a distinct set of ethical and societal challenges, which have started to be considered as the sector is advancing.

These entail the moral use of human tissue, issues of consent and ownership, data protection, commercial exploitation, gendered innovations and fair access to resulting therapies. Responsible governance of emerging biotechnologies must anticipate these challenges rather than react to them retroactively and for this researchers and innovators involved in this field, as well as R&I managers and actors responsible of their governance at all levels, should familiarize with these topics.

Furthermore, public trust, equitable access, media framing, and global policy coordination all play significant roles in shaping how organoid innovations are received, regulated, and integrated into healthcare realms and society at large. A responsive, equitable, and participatory approach to governance can help ensure that organoid innovation serves the public good.

3.3.1 Consent

Informed consent represents the highest expression of respect and protection for a person's right to autonomy and self-determination.

3.3.1.1 The Limitations of One-Time Consent

Traditional biomedical research often employs a broad, one-time consent model for tissue donation. While administratively straightforward, this approach can be ethically problematic when applied to organoid research. The potential uses of donated tissue in organoid science are expansive, and they may evolve significantly over time—ranging from fundamental research to commercial development or clinical application. One-time consent may not adequately capture these future contingencies, leading to gaps in informed participation (Dennerlein et al., 2022).

3.3.1.2 Dynamic Consent Models and Donor Expectations

To address these challenges, scholars and ethicists have advocated for dynamic consent frameworks in which donors should be informed not only about the storage and analysis of their samples, but also about potential secondary uses of their genomic and health data. These models facilitate ongoing communication between researchers and donors, allowing individuals to modify their consent preferences as research contexts change. Consent models should include options to withdraw data, restrict certain uses, or request updates on research outcomes (Sipp et al., 2022).

Digital platforms can support real-time updates and facilitate opt-in or opt-out mechanisms for specific types of use. While promising, dynamic consent models require significant infrastructural investment and raise questions about digital literacy and equity.

Research suggests that tissue donors often expect some degree of control or awareness over the use of their biological material, even if they legally relinquish ownership (Niemansburg et al., 2017; Boers et al., 2018). Transparency about downstream applications, particularly when organoids are used in commercial settings or in transplantation protocols, is crucial to maintaining trust.

3.3.1.3 Special Considerations in Vulnerable Populations

When sourcing tissue from children, individuals with cognitive disabilities, or economically disadvantaged populations, additional ethical safeguards are required. These include enhanced consent procedures, independent advocacy, and community consultation. Ensuring that vulnerable groups are not disproportionately targeted for tissue collection without clear

pathways to benefit sharing is a central tenet of ethical research design (Dennerlein et al., 2022).

3.3.2 Commercialization, Ownership and Benefit Sharing

As organoid technologies transition from research laboratories to commercial applications, ethical questions surrounding ownership, intellectual property (IP), and benefit sharing come to the forefront. The commercialization of organoids raises tension between innovation incentives and fairness, especially when products are developed from publicly funded research or donated biological materials.

3.3.2.1 Intellectual Property and Ownership

Most jurisdictions do not recognize human biological materials, once donated, as the property of the individual donor. However, the organoids derived from these materials can be subject to IP protections, such as patents or trade secrets. This legal dichotomy creates ethical dissonance: while donors relinquish control, companies may generate significant profit from downstream innovations built on those same materials (Niemansburg et al., 2017).

The ethical stakes are particularly high when organoids are developed for clinical use. For instance, if a biotech firm uses patient-derived iPSCs to produce kidney or liver -s for regenerative therapy, the question arises: who owns the product? And should the donor share in the financial benefits? Current practice tends to exclude donors from ownership or profit-sharing, but some scholars argue for models of partial attribution or benefit arrangements.

Various approaches have been proposed to address the fairness of commercialization in organoid research. These include:

- **Monetary benefit sharing:** Donors receive a share of profits derived from their biological materials (though this is rare and legally complex and can open the door to the idea of turning body parts into commodities).
- **Community benefit:** Resources are directed back into the communities or hospitals that supplied the samples.
- **Access commitments:** Companies agree to provide any resulting therapies at reduced cost in under-resourced settings.

While these models are aspirational, their implementation has been uneven and context-dependent. Ethics committees and institutional review boards (IRBs) must play a greater role in evaluating benefit-sharing arrangements during research approval and commercialization phases.

3.3.2.2 Transparency in Commercialization Pathways

Transparency about potential commercial uses of organoids is often lacking in early-stage research settings. Patients and donors may not be informed that their tissue will be used to develop a marketable product. Even when consent is obtained, it may not adequately convey the economic value chain involved. Responsible governance models should include robust disclosure requirements for commercial intent and offer opportunities for donors to opt out of commercial pathways.

3.3.2.3 Public Funding and Private Profit

The majority of organoid platforms have their origins in publicly funded academic research. As these technologies are transferred to industry via licensing or spin-off ventures, concerns arise

about the public's return on investment. Critics argue that public benefit should be a guiding principle in licensing agreements. This might include pricing controls, non-exclusive licensing for essential technologies, or reinvestment in basic research infrastructure (Dennerlein et al., 2022).

Some scholars also highlights the need for transparency in partnerships between public institutions and private entities. Without ethical guardrails, such collaborations may appear exploitative or create conflicts of interest that erode public trust.

3.3.3 Clinical Trial Ethics

As organoids move from preclinical research into early-phase human trials, ethical concerns around trial design, participant safety, and regulatory oversight become more prominent. The unique characteristics of organoid-based interventions demand heightened ethical scrutiny. In general, the ethical conduct of organoid clinical trials requires a recalibration of existing norms to reflect the distinct features of this emerging therapeutic class.

3.3.3.1 Trial Design and Ethical Oversight

Organoid-based therapies are currently being evaluated in first-in-human studies under compassionate use or experimental frameworks. These trials often involve patients with few or no existing therapeutic options, which heightens vulnerability and the potential for therapeutic misconception. Clear communication of risk, scientific uncertainty, and trial goals is therefore essential (de Jongh et al., 2022).

Institutional review boards (IRBs) must be adequately equipped to assess the novel risks associated with organoid therapies (Bunnik et al., 2022), including immune rejection, tumorigenicity, and long-term functional integration.

3.3.3.2 Informed Consent in Complex Interventions

Obtaining informed consent in organoid-based trials presents challenges beyond standard biomedical protocols. Patients must understand not only the risks of the intervention but also the uncertainty surrounding efficacy, scalability, and long-term outcomes. This is particularly relevant for autologous organoid transplants derived from patient-specific iPSCs.

Effective consent requires plain language communication, visual aids, and repeated opportunities for posing questions. Researchers should also consider involving patient advocates or ethics consultants in the consent process to ensure adequate comprehension.

3.3.3.3 Inclusion and Equity in Participant Selection

Ethical trial design also entails equitable participant selection. Organoid trials must avoid excluding underrepresented groups due to socioeconomic, geographic, or linguistic barriers. At the same time, vulnerable populations should not be disproportionately targeted for high-risk experimental interventions without appropriate safeguards.

Sipp et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of inclusive trial protocols and culturally sensitive engagement strategies. Recruiting diverse populations is not only an ethical imperative but also a scientific necessity for generalizing trial findings.

3.3.3.4 Post-Trial Responsibilities

The conclusion of a trial does not end researchers' ethical obligations. Participants may face long-term effects that require monitoring, even if the initial study period has ended. Furthermore, if the

therapy proves successful, issues of access and affordability must be addressed.

Ethical frameworks should include provisions for post-trial care, data sharing with participants, and transparent communication about next steps. As organoid therapies evolve, long-term registries and post-market surveillance mechanisms will be essential for tracking efficacy and safety over time (Dennerlein et al., 2022).

3.3.4 Moral Status and Ontology

Although non-neural organoids do not present the same level of ethical concern as brain organoids regarding consciousness or sentience, the question of their moral status is increasingly relevant as the technology evolves. As organoids grow more complex, especially when they exhibit vascularization, responsiveness to stimuli, or are integrated into host organisms, ethical questions emerge about the degree of moral consideration they deserve (Mollaki, 2021).

3.3.4.1 Defining the Moral Status of Organoids

In biomedical ethics, moral status typically depends on attributes such as sentience, cognition, or potential for personhood. Most current non-brain organoids do not meet these criteria. However, their increasing physiological sophistication challenges clear demarcations. For instance, gut organoids with peristaltic movement or liver organoids capable of metabolic activity may warrant moral scrutiny even in the absence of nervous system function (Niemansburg et al., 2017).

The ethical question is not whether organoids are persons, but whether their complexity demands new normative considerations, such as limits on their use in certain experiments, ethical treatment during long-term cultivation, or restrictions on integration with animal models.

3.3.4.2 Composite Systems and Chimeric Use

A particularly contentious issue involves the use of organoids in chimeric research, where human-derived organoids are implanted into animal hosts. While this is most ethically fraught with brain organoids, non-neural organoids still raise concerns when implanted into functional organ systems. Questions include whether such interventions alter the identity of the host organism and whether they might inadvertently produce sentient or partially humanized tissues.

According to the HYBRIDA project (Gaillard, 2025), these composite biological systems may create new ethical and regulatory gray zones. The challenge is to identify meaningful thresholds of complexity that warrant review or regulation, even in the absence of cognitive capacity.

3.3.4.3 Symbolic and Cultural Dimensions

Beyond biological features, moral status is often shaped by cultural narratives and public perception. For example, the use of organoids for creating reproductive tissues or fetal models, though not widespread, has triggered symbolic concerns about “playing God” or overstepping natural boundaries.

Public responses to biomedical innovation often depend as much on social meaning as on scientific accuracy. Ethics frameworks must therefore account for symbolic dimensions of organoid science and engage with societal values in transparent, respectful ways.

3.3.5 Data Governance and Privacy

Organoid research frequently involves the use of patient-derived biological material, often paired with genetic sequencing, clinical data, and digital modeling. As a result, it raises substantial concerns about privacy, data security, and the long-term stewardship of sensitive health information.

3.3.5.1 Identifiability of Organoid-Derived Data

Even when organoid samples are anonymized, they often retain genomic and phenotypic markers that could potentially be traced back to the donor. As noted by Niemansburg et al. (2017), advances in AI and bioinformatics can enhance the risk of re-identification, particularly when datasets are combined across platforms. Furthermore, for donors with rare genetic conditions it is even less feasible.

Even if this case clashes with privacy, from a further perspective, it can be a desirable achievement. In fact, full de-identification reduces scientific and clinical value. Without linking organoids to personal and biological data, they are unsuitable for precision medicine, limiting their use in diagnosis, drug testing, and returning results to donors.

Moreover, de-identification hampers long-term follow-up, making it harder to validate models or gather valuable longitudinal data, ultimately diminishing the utility of organoids as research tools (de Jongh et al., 2022).

Patients themselves can also ask to retain control of the research use of organoids stemmed from their cells (Boers et al., 2018) and this can be possible only in case of de-anonymized cell donation.

3.3.5.2 Data Stewardship

Robust data stewardship involves clear policies for data retention, auditing, and encryption. Institutions conducting organoid research should implement best practices in cybersecurity, access control, and ethical review of data use. These standards should be transparently communicated to participants and the public.

3.3.6 Gendered Innovation

An emerging ethical consideration in organoid science involves gendered innovation—recognizing and integrating sex and gender analysis into the design and application of biomedical research. Historically, biomedical research has often defaulted to male-derived samples or overlooked sex-specific physiological differences, leading to diagnostic and therapeutic disparities. Organoid research risks replicating these biases if it does not actively ensure that both male and female biological samples are equally represented in biobanks and experimental models.

3.3.6.1 Gendered clinical research

Gendered innovation is particularly relevant in the clinical translation of organoid technologies. Sex-specific responses to drug metabolism, disease progression, and organ function must inform the design of organoid-based therapies and testing protocols. For example, studies have shown that kidney function, hormonal activity, and immune responses can differ significantly between sexes, influencing treatment outcomes. Failure to disaggregate data

by sex or design inclusive trials may perpetuate existing gender gaps in medical efficacy and safety.

By embedding gendered analysis into all stages of organoid research, from tissue sourcing and biobank composition to data interpretation and clinical trial design, researchers can foster more ethical, effective, and equitable science. This requires not only scientific diligence but also institutional commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion as core values of responsible innovation.

3.3.6.2 Gender inclusion

Furthermore, attention to gender must extend beyond biological sex to include broader gender identities and social determinants of health. Inclusive research practices should ensure that data collection, informed consent processes, and participant engagement reflect the diversity of gender experiences. This includes adapting language, minimizing barriers to participation for marginalized gender groups, and avoiding normative assumptions in trial design.

3.3.7 Public Perception and Trust

Public attitudes toward biomedical innovations can influence policy development, research funding, and market adoption. Organoids are not yet widely understood outside scientific and clinical communities, but early studies suggest a mix of curiosity, hope, and ethical caution among the public. Citizens tend to support organoid research when it is framed around therapeutic potential, particularly for otherwise untreatable conditions. However, concerns arise around commercialization, tissue sourcing, and the potential for unintended uses (Ravn et al., 2023).

The lack of transparency in some biotech pipelines, coupled with inconsistent communication from researchers, can erode trust. Building a socially sustainable organoid ecosystem will require proactive engagement with diverse publics. This includes clear explanation of benefits and risks, honest accounting of uncertainties, and inclusive deliberative processes to understand public values.

3.3.8 Health Equity and Global Disparities

Organoid innovations risk exacerbating existing health and research inequities. The technology is currently concentrated in high-resource settings with access to advanced lab infrastructure, skilled personnel, and funding. Meanwhile, low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) may provide tissue samples or participate in global biobanking efforts without reaping proportional clinical or economic benefits.

Within countries, disparities in healthcare access can limit who benefits from organoid-based diagnostics or therapies. Personalized medicine platforms derived from patient-specific organoids could remain inaccessible to populations underrepresented in biobanks or living in regions with limited insurance coverage. Especially in the case of scenarios of “organs printed on demand”, a ‘social stratification of biofabrication’ (Vermeulen et al., 2017) could potentially emerge, where those who can afford personalized organs can live longer and enjoy better quality of life without the need for immune-suppressant drugs. Meanwhile, others will depend on scarce donor organs and endure lifelong drug treatments to prevent rejection.

Without deliberate efforts to promote inclusion and affordability, the clinical promise of organoids may reinforce rather than reduce structural inequalities.

3.3.9 Media Narratives and Hype Management

Media representations shape public discourse about emerging technologies. Organoids have received increasing coverage in both scientific journalism and mainstream news, often accompanied by optimistic headlines about “mini-organs,” “lab-grown tissues,” or “organ replacement on demand.”

While these framings can generate excitement and attract funding, they also risk misrepresenting the current state of the science. Unrealistic expectations may lead to disillusionment or ethical backlash if clinical breakthroughs are delayed (Bredenoord et al., 2017).

Responsible communication from both journalists and scientists is essential to ensure that public narratives reflect both the promise and limitations of organoid research.

3.3.10 Societal Dialogue and Participatory Governance

Inclusive and participatory approaches to science governance are key to aligning organoid innovation with societal needs and values. Rather than treating public engagement as an afterthought, innovation communities should embed it early and often throughout the research and development process (Simone et al., 2025).

Citizen panels, stakeholder workshops, and co-design initiatives can help identify priorities, explore concerns, and build legitimacy. These processes should not be limited to one-off consultations but integrated as iterative practices that shape decision-making and accountability mechanisms.

4. REFLECTION WORKSHOP ON SOCIO-ETHICAL ISSUES OF ORGANOID RESEARCH AND FUTURE CLINICAL DEVELOPMENT

4.1 Introduction

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) places particular emphasis on the transition from research to real-world application, when scientific developments move from the lab into society. In the health context, this shift occurs most visibly in hospitals and among patients.

The ENLIGHT project seeks to demonstrate the technical feasibility of designing and producing an effective artificial pancreas for drug testing and disease modelling. However, alongside this technological advancement, ethical and societal issues inevitably arise. Public perceptions, concerns, fears, and expectations regarding these innovations are not yet fully understood or addressed.

To this end, a reflection workshop focused on the ENLIGHT's technologies is closely aligned with the core values of RRI. Such a setting allows ENLIGHT partners to ask crucial questions: *What responsibility issues must be acknowledged and addressed before it becomes too late to influence outcomes responsibly, as cautioned by the Collingridge dilemma?*

The goal of the workshop was then to encourage collective reflection and discussion among ENLIGHT partners on the socio-ethical dimensions of organoid research and its future clinical applications. The discussion was grounded in the achievements of the ENLIGHT project and aimed to explore how organoid research can be conducted responsibly beyond the project's scope and into future developments, taking seriously into consideration values, needs and expectations of societal actors.

The workshop structure differs from other well-established "RRI thinking tools" like the Societal Readiness Thinking Tool (Bernstein et al., 2022), which is a practical guide for scientists and engineers looking to incorporate social and ethical responsibility into their work. The workshop method has been grounded on specific societal and ethical issues connected to the organoid sector and mainly raised by citizens involved in a participatory exercise. As such, it can complement and enhance other RRI thinking tools, which are more oriented toward general RRI guiding questions.

The Reflection Workshop took place on April 9th 2025 in Utrecht, at the UMC premises, concluding the ENLIGHT Spring Consortium Meeting at the very end of the project.

The session lasted 1.5 hours and involved 12 participants from various sectors, including academia, the private sector, and civil society organizations. Of these, 10 attended in person and 2 joined online. Bassetti Foundation was the designer and the facilitator of the workshop.

The workshop centered on sharing a summary of the data derived from the analysis conducted by Fondazione Bassetti, with a particular focus on discussing the outcomes of deliberative processes involving EU citizens on this topic.

As a prompt for discussion, the Bassetti Foundation presented the results of three deliberative exercises conducted within the [EU H2020 project HYBRIDA](#). To date, there are no further

examples of deliberative processes on organoids, and this initiative represents a relevant exercise at the EU level with a clear focus on this technological field. Some previous studies have involved citizens or patients or caregivers in participatory-like approaches to gather insights on concerns and opinions from societal actors on organoids, but the HYBRIDA workshops' results, with its comprehensive set of socio-ethical issues directly raised by EU citizens, was ideal to be used as a starting point for the discussion, with the aim of:

- Raising awareness within the ENLIGHT consortium about public perceptions of organoid research and its applications;
- Stimulating reflection on the socio-ethical implications of ENLIGHT's developments;
- Familiarizing researchers with anticipatory and inclusive approaches in the design and implementation of research and innovation projects, potentially laying the groundwork for future citizen engagement activities.

4.2 The approach

The workshop was structured into five main stages:

1. Recap of the RRI Approach

The first part of the workshop recalled the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach, outlining its definition and key dimensions. Particular attention was given to the importance of understanding public perceptions of science and new technologies, methods for gathering public opinion, and citizen engagement strategies.

2. Presentation of HYBRIDA Public Debate Results

Some of results of a public debate on organoids, conducted as part of the EU HYBRIDA project¹ and documented in a scientific publication (Ravn et al., 2023), were presented. Data on public perception on brain organoids were excluded.

3. Discussion on Perceived Benefits

Through a structured dialogue, ENLIGHT researchers discussed the short- and medium-term benefits of organoid research conducted within the project, using the benefits identified by the citizens involved in the HYBRIDA project deliberative exercise as a starting point.

4. Exploration of Citizens' Concerns

Similar to the previous stage, this phase focused on concerns raised by citizens during the HYBRIDA project exercise. With support from the Bassetti Foundation, ENLIGHT researchers examined these concerns from ethical, social, and scientific perspectives.

5. Concluding Discussion on Responsibility Issues

The final stage involved a discussion on responsibility-related issues and proposed solutions, as identified through the HYBRIDA process. This discussion concluded with the formulation of a list of potentially relevant themes for responsible (bioprinted) organoid R&I.

¹ The debate consisted of three deliberative workshops held in Greece, Italy, and Denmark.

◀ Figures 1 and 2 - The discussion on the benefits and concerns

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Benefits

Building on the perspectives shared by citizens in the HYBRIDA project deliberative exercise, researchers discussed and identified the benefits of organoid research conducted within the ENLIGHT project.

All participants agreed that citizens “are very well on point,” demonstrating a clear and accurate understanding of the advantages associated with organoid research and its future developments.

At the request of the Bassetti Foundation, researchers categorized these benefits into short-term and long-term, as outlined below:

SHORT-TERM	MEDIUM/LONG TERMS – 20 years?
Drug testing/ screening	Auto-transplantation
Personalized medicine	
Potential reduced use of animals in research experiments	
Potential reduction of costs	

Drug testing and screening represent the core benefit of the ENLIGHT project and are the primary objectives to be achieved within its timeframe.

Closely linked to this is the potential to test targeted treatments on organoids derived from patients’ cells. This paves the way for personalized medicine, a promising development that could be realized in the near future.

Another possible short-term advancement of organoid research is the reduction in animal use.

While organoids can significantly decrease the number of animals needed for drug testing, the ENLIGHT consortium raised an important point for consideration: the current process of matrix development for culturing organoids and induced pluripotent stem cells still relies on Matrigel, a material obtained from the matrix produced by tumoral cells transplanted in mice. This practice raises ethical concerns, even though all three 3R (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) principles are observed, and may offset some of the anticipated reduction in animal use for preclinical experiments. Although ENLIGHT has not thoroughly investigated the replacement of Matrigel as component for stem cell expansion and culture, it remains a critical topic for future research and public communication to ensure transparency and foster trust with society.

In addition, the ENLIGHT team identified a further potential benefit: the reduction of costs. Researchers noted that 3D printing can streamline drug development processes, making them more efficient and ultimately more affordable. However, this expected cost-saving might be impacted by additional expenses related to 3D printing patents. While ENLIGHT does not currently have data on this matter, it is an important factor to consider.

When discussing the medium-term benefits, such as auto-transplantation and the development of advanced treatments for genetic diseases, researchers reflected on what would be a realistic timeframe to communicate, one that avoids generating excessive hype or unrealistic expectations that could ultimately undermine public trust in the field.

At the same time, participants emphasized that the timeline for concrete clinical results is very much tissue-dependent and for instance in the case of less complex tissues and organs, like skin, clinical outcomes are already available. Or in the case of transplantation of islet organoids, which are not bioprinted, clinical trials are already established and thus will provide faster results.

As for auto-transplantation, some participants pointed out that this may not be the direction the field is heading, at least for application in therapies for type 1 diabetes, for which autoimmunity to beta cells can reoccur.

Moreover, they highlighted that creating personalized organoid lines for each patient would be extremely costly and time-consuming, making it an impractical path for large-scale implementation. Currently, a main direction in the field is the generation of islets from (donor-derived) stem cells, using cells engineered to display a hypoimmune profile.

4.3.2 Concerns

In response to the concerns raised during the HYBRIDA project's participatory workshops, grouped into three key categories (as illustrated below), researchers expressed views that often differed from those of the public.

Commercialization: Industry Monopoly over Organoid Technologies

Increased health inequalities/ Reinforced existing hierarchies among different types of illnesses as to the allocation of funding, research, and treatment

Researchers acknowledged these concerns but noted that they are not unique to organoids since they apply broadly across the healthcare system. While personalized medicine may currently be costly, some researchers suggested that these costs could decrease over time. Others highlighted that regulatory mechanisms exist to help control the pricing of drugs and therapies.

Therapeutics are overpriced and not properly distributed within and among populations.

Researchers agreed that current global disparities in infrastructure in this field pose a challenge. However, they expressed optimism that although organoids may initially benefit wealthier countries, their use could eventually expand to emerging economies as technologies become more accessible.

Privacy and Data Management: Data Storage and Use

Genetic data is used by insurance to deny access to treatments and therapies

While this specific issue was not extensively discussed, related concerns emerged during other parts of the workshop.

Researchers highlighted two main points:

- **Geographical inequality** in infrastructure for cell and data storage exists worldwide, which can lead to uneven access and capabilities beyond just organoid research.
- **Alternative models of consent**, such as dynamic consent, should be explored further to ensure privacy is protected but also donors' interest to be part of the innovation process, as discussed later in the workshop.

Dual Use: Military and Ethical Concerns

Organoids used for biological warfare/Development of soldiers with augmented physical abilities

The ENLIGHT consortium considered these concerns highly unlikely in the current context. They argued that simpler and more cost-effective technologies already exist for military purposes, making organoids an improbable choice. While physical enhancement is technically possible and worth monitoring, researchers did not see organoids as the key technology enabling it.

◀ Figure 3

- The final session of the workshop on responsibility-related "issues"

4.3.3 Issues

Based on the concerns raised by the public during the deliberative exercise conducted within the HYBRIDA project, three key areas of responsibility were discussed:

Ownership of Organoids

Researchers generally agreed that ownership lies with “those who develop the protocols used to create them.” A broader debate emerged, closely related to the issue of compensation, about whether individuals who possess peculiar cells that enable the development of specific organoids have a claim to ownership. This raises important considerations regarding the extent of ownership over what is created from one’s own cells or tissues. Perspectives varied: some participants compared cell and tissue donation to blood donation, while others highlighted the need to differentiate between the donation itself and the resulting products developed after manipulation.

Remuneration/Compensation for Cell/Tissue Donors

This topic, closely linked to ownership, also revealed diverse opinions. Some researchers argued that, like blood or organ donation, cell donation should remain unpaid. Others countered that the comparison does not fully apply, as donated cells may be used to develop marketable products. While no consensus was reached, there was general agreement that this is a complex issue requiring further dialogue, both within the scientific community and with the broader public, given the range of ethical perspectives involved.

Dynamic Consent

Researchers recognized dynamic consent as a promising tool to support research while respecting participants’ privacy and autonomy. However, they also acknowledged several challenges. Effective implementation may require significant infrastructure investment and could conflict with data anonymization efforts. Additionally, it is often unrealistic to anticipate all future uses of donated biological material. Therefore, a comprehensive and interdisciplinary discussion, including legal, ethical, and technical expertise, is essential to properly address this issue.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ON ORGANOIDS

Organoids represent one of the most promising and rapidly advancing frontiers in biomedical science, with transformative implications for research, diagnostics, and regenerative medicine. For the innovation community, the challenge now lies not only in refining the technology, but in ensuring that its development and deployment reflect shared ethical standards and social priorities.

This report has shown that the ethical and societal aspects of organoid research are not secondary considerations, but integral to the success and sustainability of the field. As the science matures, so must the frameworks that guide it. Institutions must invest in foresight, transparency, and engagement to build innovation cultures that are both competitive and accountable.

The current trajectory of organoid research is already intersecting with bioprinting technology, as ENLIGHT has demonstrated, and in the future will likely intersect with other transformative technologies, including AI-driven drug discovery. These convergences will amplify both the opportunities and the socio-ethical complexity of biomedical innovation. Thus, even more interdisciplinary collaboration will be essential not only between scientists and ethicists but across law, policy, social science, and public engagement domains.

Equally, efforts to democratize the benefits of organoid innovation, through equitable licensing, open access platforms, and capacity-building in under-resourced regions, will be critical to ensuring global justice.

The analysis of socio-ethical aspects of organoid R&I as well as the ENLIGHT Reflection Workshop have been conducive to a list of recommendations for researchers and innovators working in the (bioprinted) organoid field to implement a responsible conduct of R&I in organoids.

These recommendations can be a guiding light for future development of the ENLIGHT pathway and thus for the whole ENLIGHT consortium but can also pave the way for further reflection and discussion among the scientific community at large about responsibility issues and concerns to consider to maximize the benefits that this emerging technological field can bring to the society.

Enhance Consent Practices

- **Move beyond one-time consent:** Traditional consent models fail to address the evolving nature of organoid research. Dynamic consent allows donors to stay informed and involved as their biological materials are used in new contexts. It enables ongoing communication and options to opt-in, opt-out, or revise consent based on updated research directions. Exploring procedural and technical constraints and how to move forward in this domain is essential.
- **Ensure transparency:** Researchers must clearly explain the potential scope of research, including future clinical applications or commercial uses. This promotes trust and aligns with participants' expectations to be part of the process.

- **Protect vulnerable populations:** Special ethical protocols must be adopted when sourcing tissue from minors, individuals with limited decision-making capacity, or economically disadvantaged populations. These should include the presence of independent advocates and enhanced community dialogue to ensure fair and informed participation.

Address Ownership and Benefit Sharing

- **Contribute to legal and ethical ownership discussion:** The ambiguity around who owns organoids - especially if they are finalized thanks to bioprinting mechanisms - and the derived products must be discussed. Researchers should contribute to a broader discussion on biological donations and the resulting biotechnological products.
- **Explore benefit-sharing models:** Consider approaches such as non-monetary community benefits, reinvestment in public research, or tiered access programs to ensure that donors and their communities are not excluded from the benefits of innovation. Set-up of engagement mechanisms to identify what societal actors would like to have as tangible rewards should also be envisaged.
- **Ensure public return on investment:** When research is publicly funded, mechanisms should be in place to guarantee societal benefit, such as affordable access, transparency in licensing agreements, and open innovation initiatives. Again, a broad public discussion as well as deliberation exercises could be envisaged to define the best options.

Strengthen Clinical Trial Ethics

- **Design inclusive and equitable trials:** Trials must recruit diverse participants to avoid biases. Strategies should be developed to overcome language, geographic, or socioeconomic barriers.
- **Support informed consent:** Given the complexity of organoid-based interventions, informed consent must include multiple layers of explanation, opportunities for clarification, and decision aids. Patient advocates should support this process.
- **Plan for post-trial responsibilities:** Ethical obligations continue after trials end. Researchers must offer continued care or monitoring and communicate outcomes and access plans for therapies that prove successful.

Protect Data and Privacy

- **Recognize limits of anonymization:** Genetic and phenotypic data, especially from rare disease cell or tissue samples, carry re-identification risks. Researchers must communicate these risks and secure participant consent accordingly. At the same time, the potential benefits of this process should be investigated and if suitable for specific clinical or research pathways, shared and agreed upon by donors.
- **Foster robust data stewardship:** Institutions must implement best practices in data handling, including encryption, limited access protocols, regular audits, and transparent data governance policies. These practices should be clearly communicated to participants.

Integrate Gender and Diversity Considerations

- **Avoid sex-based biases:** Ensure that both male and female samples are equally represented in biobanks and study designs to avoid systemic biases in outcomes.
- **Embed gender analysis:** Research should investigate how biological sex affects disease progression and drug responses. These insights must inform design and analysis in organoid-based studies.
- **Include gender diversity:** Design inclusive consent forms and trial protocols that reflect the full spectrum of gender identities and account for social determinants of health. Engagement strategies should be culturally sensitive and respectful.

Foster Public Participation and Transparent Dialogue

- **Engage early and continuously:** Public engagement should not be an afterthought. Embed it throughout the R&D process via citizen panels, deliberative dialogues, and stakeholder workshops. Patient co-creation mechanisms should be also explored.
- **Communicate responsibly:** Avoid exaggerated claims about imminent cures or simplistic statements (“organoid technology will reduce animal testing”) without considering blind spots. Clear, honest communication helps set realistic expectations and strengthens trust.
- **Address symbolic concerns:** Be mindful of cultural and ethical sensitivities, such as fears about “playing God” or unnatural manipulation. These narratives shape public acceptance and must be taken seriously.

Promote Global and Health Equity

- **Bridge global disparities:** Ensure that organoid technologies are accessible to LMICs through equitable technology transfer, training, and collaborative research structures.
- **Tackle local inequities:** Work with health systems to make personalized organoid-based therapies accessible to underserved populations. Consider insurance coverage, pricing strategies, and public financing mechanisms.

Institutionalize Responsible Innovation Practices

- **Adopt anticipatory governance tools:** Use RRI tools to identify potential risks, ethical concerns, and social implications early in the research lifecycle.
- **Encourage interdisciplinary oversight:** Ethics committees should include not just researchers, but also legal scholars, patient representatives, and civil society voices to ensure comprehensive oversight.
- **Support reflective practice:** Facilitate workshops and structured reflection spaces to engage researchers in proactive thinking about the ethical and societal impact of their work.

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**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964497.